

Magnetic Bridge Concept

This new concept of bridges uses a series of panels that have magnets at the bottom of it and use Earth's magnetic field to levitate at a certain distance from Earth, making the need for the bridge's legs useless.

Using these futuristic bridges concept may one day eliminate the need for legs since all the panels levitate from the ground.

This technology may even connect entire countries or continents thus making the dream of very long-distance bridges a reality.

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